

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	The use of Artificial Intelligence in dental imaging for endodontics: A Systematic Review	Page 1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	<p>Background - This systematic review examines AI's role in Endodontics, and the main objective was focused on its use with dental imaging (dental radiographs and CBCT).</p> <p>Methods - We searched Scopus, PubMed/MEDLINE, EMBASE, and IEEE using MeSH terms for English-language articles on AI in endodontics. Of 304 initial articles identified, 32 met inclusion criteria, that were in vivo studies of endodontic morphology, pathologies or treatment, machine learning aspects, dental imaging methods, datasets, AI models, geographical origins, and metrics.</p> <p>Results - Initial search identified 304 articles, reduced to 32 after removing duplicates and ineligible articles. AI in dental imaging accurately evaluates root canal morphology, treatments, and periapical radiolucencies. Artificial neural networks are the predominant AI model.</p> <p>Conclusion – AI holds promise in enhancing Endodontics. Ethical guidelines are essential for AI projects. Standardized protocols for AI in healthcare and dental care are needed. The shortage of reliable datasets and dental images is a current limitation.</p> <p>Funding: No funding</p> <p>Prospero Registration: CRD42022333404 on 05/28/2022</p>	Page 1
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	The use of AI in dentistry is becoming very helpful for the dentists analysing and interpreting 2D and 3d dental imaging. It's been used in several dental specialties and endodontics is one of them. This systematic review aims to determine and compile the use, advantages, and benefits of AI applications in endodontics using different 2D and 3D dental imaging modalities.	Pages 2, 3
Objectives	4	The objective of this systematic review was to assess the use and benefits of AI in Endodontics with any dental imaging (dental radiographs and CBCT).	Page 3
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	<p>Population: We included any study design for living people, who underwent endodontic treatment for root canal morphology or anatomy evaluation, root canal treatment evaluation and results; periapical lesion or radiolucencies detection and diagnosis; root fracture detection and prognosis.</p> <p>Intervention: Any AI application with any dental imaging (Panoramic or OPG; Periapical or Intraoral; Cone Beam Computed Tomography; or a multimodal approach</p> <p>Comparison: None</p> <p>Outcome: The applications and benefits of AI in dental imaging for endodontics</p>	Pages 3,4
Information sources	6	Scopus (Elsevier), PubMed/MEDLINE (National Library of Medicine), EMBASE (Elsevier) and IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers).	Page 4
Search strategy	7	<p>In a period between May and June of 2022 the author N.P. conducted the searches on the electronic bases, mentioned item 2.3.1, using the Mesh terms mentioned on item 2.3.2, using the search strategy mentioned on item 2.3.3.</p> <p>2.3.1. The electronic searched bases were: Scopus (Elsevier), PubMed/MEDLINE (National Library of Medicine), EMBASE (Elsevier) and IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers). The search comprised the period between 2000 and 2022, performed on June, 2022.</p> <p>2.3.2. The Medical Subject Heading (Mesh) terms and synonyms were: Endodontics (Endodontics Treatment; Root Canal Treatment; Root Canal Therapy; RCT; Endodontic Filling; Endodontic Lesion; Periapical Radiolucency; Periapical pathology; Periapical pathosis; Periapical Periodontitis; Apical Periodontitis; Apical Radiolucency; Apical pathology;</p>	Pages 4,5

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		<p>Apical pathosis).</p> <p>Artificial Intelligence (Machine Learning; Deep Learning; Artificial Neural Network; Convolutional Neural Network).</p> <p>Dental Imaging (Dental Radiograph; Dental Radiology; Dental X-ray; Panoramic; OPG; Cone Beam Computed Tomography; Periapical Radiograph; Periapical Radiology; Periapical X-ray; Intraoral Radiograph; Intraoral Radiology; Intraoral X-ray);</p> <p>2.3.3. The search strategy:</p> <p>The following search strategy was used: ((endodontics OR "endodontics treatment" OR "Root Canal Treatment" OR "Root Canal Therapy" OR "Endodontic Filling" OR "Periapical Lesion" OR "Endodontic Lesion" OR "Periapical Radiolucency" OR "Periapical pathology" OR "Periapical pathosis" OR "Periapical Periodontitis" OR "Apical Periodontitis" OR "Apical Radiolucency" OR "Apical pathology" OR "Apical pathosis") AND ("Artificial intelligence" OR "Machine Learning" OR "Deep Learning" OR "Artificial Neural Network" OR "Convolutional Neural Network") AND ("Dental Imaging" OR "Dental Radiograph" OR "Dental Radiology" OR "Dental X-ray" OR Panoramic OR opg OR cbct OR "Cone Beam Computed Tomography" OR "Periapical Radiograph" OR "Periapical Radiology" OR "Periapical X-ray" OR "Intraoral Radiograph" OR "Intraoral Radiology" OR "Intraoral X-ray" OR Orthopantomogram OR Pantomogram OR Orthopantomograph))</p>	
Selection process	8	The screening of the papers was performed by three authors (M.H., R.B. and Z.B.) with the use of the online web system RAYYAN(Ouzzani et al., 2016a) in the "Blind On" mode activated. The disagreements were solved by consensus within these 3 authors or by a fourth author (T.K.), who had been previously designated to evaluate such case. All titles and abstracts were read, and the studies that did not match the inclusion criteria were excluded. The Included articles were exported as a comma-separated value (csv) file.	Pages 5,6
Data collection process	9	The data extraction was conducting by importing the electronic (csv) file from RAYYAN with the 32 included articles to a Google Docs Spreadsheet (TABLE I). All 32 studies were analyzed, and the mentioned items on (Table I) were extracted by three authors (O.T., - L.A. and R.R.), independently, and further confirmed and reviewed by a fourth author (N.P.).	Page 7
Data items	10a	<p>The data were organized in "TABLE I" with the following Topics and Sub-topics, as follows:</p> <p>Included Studies</p> <p>Machine Learning</p> <p>Modality</p> <p>Dataset Split</p> <p>Ground Truth</p> <p>Model</p> <p>Origin</p>	Page7, TABLE I
	10b	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authors; Year; - Objective; Task; - Amount, Type; - Training Set; Validation Set; Test Set; - Labeling, Annotators, Expertise - Pre-processing, Model and Architecture, Metrics; - Data Source, Country; 	Page7, TABLE I
Study risk of bias assessment	11	The quality assessment (RoB) of included studies was conducted according to the Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies, version 2 QUADAS-2 (Whiting et al., 2011), which consist of four domains: Patient Selection; Index Test; Reference Standard; Flow and Timing. The quality of each study was classified into LOW, SOME CONCERNS, AND HIGH Risk of Bias. The survey of every included study was performed by two authors (N.P. and – J.I.), independently, for the predefined consideration criteria and directed impartial appraisals, and any ambiguity was	Page 6,20 Figure III

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		settled by discussion and agreement between these 2 reviewers.	
Effect measures	12	We did not assess the effect measure; we only assessed the main characteristic of each AI application. We did not perform any meta-analysis	
Synthesis methods	13a	Since our intervention was the AI application in endodontics, we decided to included the studies that described and detailed the Goal, Task, Modality, and Machine Learning process and Metrics. We did not perform any meta-analysis	
	13b	We only synthesized the results in relation to the specific data; no other statistical analyses were performed, once that was not one of our goals. We did not perform any meta-analysis	
	13c	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
	13d	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
	13e	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
	13f	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
Reporting bias assessment	14	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
Certainty assessment	15	We did not perform any meta-analysis	

RESULTS

Study selection	16a	<pre> graph TD subgraph Identification A["Records identified (n = 304) PubMed (n = 128) Embase (n = 135) Scopus (n = 39) IEEE (n = 2)"] --> B["Duplicate records removed (n = 82)"] end A --> C["Records screened (n = 222)"] subgraph Screening C --> D["Records excluded (n = 190)"] C --> E["Reports sought for retrieval (n = 32)"] E --> F["Reports not retrieved (n = 0)"] E --> G["Reports assessed for eligibility (n = 32)"] G --> H["Reports excluded: Reason Wrong Outcome (n = 81) Reason Wrong Study Design (n = 7) Reason Wrong Publication Type (n = 8) Reason Wrong Population (n = 24) Reason Wrong Intervention (n = 69)"] end </pre>	Page 7 Figure I
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		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; display: inline-block; background-color: #e0f0ff;"> <p style="margin: 0;">Include</p> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; display: inline-block; margin-left: 10px;"> <p>Studies included in review (n = 32) Reports of included studies (n = 32)</p> </div>	
	16b	None	
Study characteristics	17	Each study characteristics can be seen in Table I	Table I
Risk of bias in studies	18	We assessed the Risk of Bias using QUADA2 and a detailed assessment of the risk of bias can be verified in the Traffic Light Plot, illustrated in the in FIGURE III – QUADAS2 – Risk of Bias Traffic Light Plot.	Page 20 Figure III
Results of individual studies	19	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
Results of syntheses	20a	<p>Goal: 54% of the papers the aimed to assess the efficiency of the ML model in detecting periapical lesion or radiolucency; 23% of the papers aimed the analysis of the root canal anatomy or morphology; 20% of the papers aimed to evaluate the root canal treatment outcome; and the last 3% of the papers aimed to detect the presence of vertical root canal fracture.</p> <p>ML Task: The Task of the ML models from each included study was analyzed and separated in four different types: Segmentation, Classification, Segmentation and Classification, and Object Detection. 44% of the studies the ML task were segmentation; 28% were</p> <p>Modality: The results reviewed that 38% of the studies used panoramic or OPG X-ray; 35% used CBCT; and 26% used periapical or intraoral X-ray.</p> <p>Dataset-split: that 34% of the studies used cross-validation, 31% used standard, in 19% data split information was not available at all, and 16% validation not available.</p> <p>Labelling process: 61% of the labeling process was done manually; Clinician diagnosis was performed in 15%; 9% was done by using CBCT; Histopathology was used in 6% of the studies. In 6% of the studies, labeling was done by software and radiology reports in 3%.</p> <p>Annotators: Overall, 28% of the studies used one annotator; 22% two annotators; 22% three annotators; 19% did not specify the number of annotators; 3% worked with four annotators; 3% with six annotators and 3% with 24 annotators.</p> <p>Annotators expertise: 30% were OMFR (Oral and Maxillo-facial Radiologists); 25% were general dentists; 20% were endodontists; 5% were students; 3% were dental pediatricians; 3% were OMFS (Oral and Maxillo-facial Surgeons); 3% were stomatologists; 3% were OMFP (Oral and Maxillo-facial Pathologists) and in 10% the specialty was not available.</p> <p>Network Architecture: 71% were CNN; 5% were random forest; 5% were support vector machine; 2% were decision tree; 2% were gradient boosting machine; 2% were GMB-transformer; 2% were k-nearest neighbors; 2% were naïve Bayes; 2% were logistic regression; 2% were backpropagation neural network; and 2% were extreme gradient booster</p> <p>Origin: In 34% of the included studies, this information was not available; in 19% the country of origin was Turkey; in 9% China; in 9% South Korea; in 9% Germany; in 3% Japan; in 3% Italy; in 3% Poland; in 3% USA; in 3% India, and in 3% the country of origin was unclear.</p>	Page 8 to 20
	20b	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
	20c	We did not perform any meta-analysis	

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	20d	We did not perform any meta-analysis	
Reporting biases	21	QUADAS2 was used	Page 20
Certainty of evidence	22	We only assessed which was the AI use in endodontics, not the quality of each application.	
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	The results suggest that AI has a great potential in Endodontics	Page 21
	23b	The availability of dental imaging dataset is an issue and trained and experienced annotators as well	Page 21
	23c	No great limitation was faced during this systematic review, the only minor was the time zones between the authors to meet when required	
	23d	AI is a very recent subject in healthcare and in dentistry, so with more studies and research it can be an enormous help and ally for the dentists	
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	CRD42022333404 on 05/28/2022	Page 1
	24b	PROSPERO	Page 1
	24c	There was no difference between the registered protocol and the current systematic review	
Support	25	NO funding support	
Competing interests	26	NO conflict of Interest from any author	
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	NO data, code and other materials are available anywhere.	

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71
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